

Panelist Sessions and Ph.D. Studies: UTAUT approach

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this paper is to examine panelist sessions and Doctor of Philosophy (Ph.D.) studies with the specific objective of analyzing Information Communication Technology (ICT) usage in panelist sessions and success in completion of Ph.D. studies. The study framework is guided by the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT). Study area is Tanzania. Quantitative method is utilized and semi-structured questionnaires were distributed to respondents at a public university using convenience sampling. The techniques used for analyzing collected data were descriptive statistics and Partial Least Square Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM) assisted with SmartPLS 3. The results revealed a significant relationship between ICT usage in panelist sessions and success in completion of Ph.D. studies ($p = 0.000$).

Keyword: panelist sessions, Ph.D. thesis, UTAUT

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1.0 INTRODUCTION

In higher education, a Doctor of Philosophy (Ph.D.) is conferred as a degree to the intended student interested in generating new knowledge through scientific research (Michalski and Fowler, 2016). Ph.D. Studies undertaken by Ph.D. students in African countries are faced with challenges such as lack of incentives at the level of the high education institutions to motivate African students to pursue higher level studies (Khodabocus, 2016). For example, Masele and Kagoya (2018) studied the connection between Information Communication Technology (ICT) and environment with a

conclusion that ergonomics should be considered by policy makers to ensure that there are appropriate facilities used in public universities.

Equally Hamilton-Ekeke and Mbachu (2015) examined institutions in relation to ICT for teaching and learning purposes. Recent results from a cross case analysis between two universities showed that other factors, such as behavioral intention has no significant effect on acceptance to new technologies in the workplace of higher education institutions (Skoumpopoulou *et al.*, 2018). Other studies have looked at ICT usage such as mobile technologies in blended distance courses, and online resources for promoting critical thinking (Shemahonge and Mbete, 2018; Samuel *et al.*, 2018; Mwalongo, 2018) but rarely on panelist sessions.

Mkwizu (2018) explored Ph.D. studies in higher education by examining Ph.D. programs and noted that mismanagement by panelists during the panelist sessions contribute to delay in completing Ph.D. programs and that in combating the situation, Ph.D. students need to shift to departments which are competent in handling panelist sessions hence building as well as enhancing a culture of competency in managing panel sessions by panelists. In addition, Mkwizu (2018) emphasized the need for more research on higher education level particularly Ph.D. programs; hence, to add on the literature of panelist sessions and Ph.D. studies. This paper examines panelist sessions and Ph.D. studies by specifically analyzing ICT usage in panelist sessions and success in completion of Ph.D. studies.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Definition of Key Concepts

2.1.1 Panelist Sessions

The postgraduate prospectus 2018/2019 of the University of Dar es Salaam states that a comprehensive examination shall be judged by a panel of experts in the relevant field who possess a Ph.D. and the panel constitutes a Principal/Dean/Director in consultation with Heads of Departments and shall have an odd number of members i.e 3 or 5 where the most senior shall chair the panel (University of Dar es Salaam, 2018). The oral examination shall not take more than three hours and that the examination may vary from one unit to another, but must examine the candidate's broad philosophical and conceptual understanding of the subject area and also their capacity to develop and communicate logical arguments (University of Dar es Salaam, 2018). This study refers to panelist sessions according to the postgraduate prospectus 2018/2019 by the University of Dar es Salaam.

Furthermore, this study is examining panelist session focusing on ICT usage in panelist sessions. Moraru (2016) pointed out that academic performance meant the quick progress rate of the Ph.D. student, aided by ICT usage to successful complete studies in stipulated period of time, among other factors. ICT Usage in this study refers to the ability of the panelist members to use recorders, videos cameras, excellent projectors, comments tracking and records information management systems during Ph.D. candidates presentations for systematically controlling the creation, distribution, use, maintenance, and disposition of recorded comments maintained as evidence of University activities in the digital era to enable students complete their studies just in time.

2.1.2 Ph.D. Studies

Doctor of Philosophy (Ph.D.) is defined as an award which is generally considered to be one of the highest academic qualifications available (Johnson, 2001, Bourner *et al.*, 2010). Ph.D. is also considered as higher degree research training and signals the beginning of a research career (Baldwin, 2014). Ph.D. studies prepare future researchers (Pearson, 2005; Fenge, 2010). Johnson (2001) noted that non-completion of Ph.D. by students may be attributed to the feeling of not owning their Ph.D.. In this paper, Ph.D. studies refer to the research training which leads to the award of Doctor of Philosophy. Spaulding and Rockinson-Szapkiv (2012) examined doctoral

candidates by concentrating on attributes of successful completion of doctoral degree. This study examines Ph.D. studies by measuring success in completion of Ph.D. studies.

2.2 Theoretical Framework

The selected theory to guide this paper is the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) which asserts that that individual's behavioral intention to use a technology is influenced by performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence, and facilitating conditions (Venkatesh *et al.*, 2003; Venkatesh *et al.*, 2012; 2016). The theory of UTAUT was developed by Venkatesh *et al.* (2003) and puts emphasis on information technology usage. The application of UTAUT is evident in studies of various scholars such as Abdelghaffar and Magdy (2012) and AlAwadh and Morris (2008). Radovan and Kristi (2017) used UTAUT to examine acceptance and use of Learning Management Systems (LMS) among higher-education teachers in the context of online learning with findings showing that information of learning processes depend on characteristics of LMS tools and the perceived usefulness of the application. Therefore, in this study, the theory of UTAUT which embraces information technology usage guides the analysis of the relationship between ICT usage in panelist sessions and success in completion of Ph.D. studies.

2.3 Empirical Literature Review

Studies in higher education have investigated various issues from technologies to critical thinking (Samuel *et al.*, 2018; Skoumpopoulou *et al.*, 2018; Mwalongo, 2018). A comparative study of two universities in Hong Kong and the UK used descriptive statistics and Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) found that for both universities, there was a high behavioural intention to use new technologies but this dimension had no effect on the staff who worked at these universities to use new technologies (Skoumpopoulou *et al.*, 2018). On the other hand, Nkoyo and Nsata (2016) explored the availability and utilization of electronic resources by postgraduate students in Nigeria. The findings from the descriptive statistics indicated that there was inadequate availability and utilization of electronic resources among postgraduates due to lack of training and inadequate supply of electricity (Nkoyo and Nsata, 2016).

Thomas and Olegajo (2017) conducted a study in Nigeria on perception of ICT using regression analysis and found that among the teacher-trainees, there was less attention to ICT attributed to attitude (3.5%), perception (3.5%), self-efficacy (2.4%), and satisfaction (1.2%). Adding to the study of ICT in higher education, Iroaganachi and Izuagbe (2018) conducted a study in Nigerian universities among the staff and revealed that ICT facilities positively impacted electronic information resource usage. Masele and Kagoya (2018) examined higher education in Tanzania and Uganda using quantitative methods and found that ICT in relation to health needed attention by policy makers.

Although literature exists on higher education addressing challenges in universities from various scholars like Nkoyo and Nsata (2016), Thomas and Oladejo (2017), Samuel *et al.* (2018), Skoumpopoulou *et al.* (2018), Masele and Kagoya (2018), Mkwizu (2018) and Mwalongo (2018), there are scant studies that examine panelist sessions and Ph.D. studies among Ph.D. students and panelists during Ph.D. proposal presentations. To bridge the knowledge gap, this study examines panelist sessions and Ph.D. studies in public universities by analyzing ICT usage in panelist sessions and success in completion of Ph.D. studies.

3. METHODOLOGY

This paper used a cross-section design with a quantitative approach to analyse the hypothesized which states that there is a positive relationship between ICT usage in panelist sessions and success in completion of Ph.D. studies. The study area for this paper is Tanzania. Data was collected from a sample size 49 Ph.D. students and panelists of University of Dar es salaam Business School in Dar es Salaam using semi-structured questionnaires.

The sampling technique used was convenience sampling. Prior pilot study was done to ensure the items in the questionnaire were valid for this study. The semi-structured questionnaires were handed to respondents to fill in and return as well as using email survey. The semi-structured questionnaire had 7 statements which measured information technology that were adapted from Mwai (2013). For the dependent variable which was success in completion of Ph.D., the 6 statements were adapted from Akbulut *et al.* (2007) and UNESCO Institute for Statistics (2006).

Using PLS algorithm in SmartPLS 3, the reliability was tested and the composite reliability values were (0.74) for ICT usage in panelist sessions and (0.79) for success in completion of Ph.D. studies. The analysis technique used to analyse collected data was descriptive statistics assisted by SPSS version 20 and Partial Least Square Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM) assisted by SmartPLS 3 to predict the significance relationship between the variables. PLS-SEM can be used for predictions as per Ringle *et al.* (2015).

4. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

The findings from Table 1 reveal that most of the respondents from Tanzania are females (53.1%), between 36 to 45 years old (51%) and have university education (100%). This implies that majority of the respondents were educated females between 36 to 45 years old.

Table 1. Respondents Demographic Information				
		Frequencies		Percentage
Age Groups	18-25	0.00		0.00%
	26-45	15		30.6%
	36-45	25		51%
	46 years and above	9		18.4%
Gender	Male	23		46.9%
	Female	26		53.1%
Education	University	49		100%

Source: Field data (2019)

In Table 2, the findings showed that majority of the respondents agreed with the statements that: the panelist should use recorders to capture comments during student presentation; ICT encompasses wide variety of devices and applications that serve to ease and enhance efficiency during the panelist session; and ICT encompasses wide variety of devices and applications that serve to ease and enhance effectiveness during the panelist session.

Table 2 also reveals that most respondent agreed to the statements that it is important to use videos and recorders during student presentation; ICT usage enables capturing, gathering, processing, storing, access and communication of information in different forms among the panelist and other stakeholders; and ICT usage builds trust and fairness during presentations. The respondents equally gave opinions on ICT usage in panelist sessions by indicating the panel members do not use video cameras during student presentation.

The descriptive results of ICT usage in panelist sessions imply that video cameras during Ph.D. presentations are not used by panel members in the panelist sessions. This suggests that most of the respondents support that panelists should use recorders and other ICT devices to enhance efficiency and effectiveness during the panelist sessions hence the ability to capture, gather, process, store, access and communicate information in different forms among the panelist and other stakeholders.

The results of this study differ from Iroaganachi and Izuagbe (2018) which found that ICT facilities positively impacted electronic information resource usage. The difference in results is because the study by Iroaganachi and Izuagbe (2018) sampled only staff views and not Ph.D. students whereas this study combined the views of both staff and Ph.D. students.

Table 2. ICT usage in Panelist Sessions

Statements	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
The panel members use video cameras during student presentation. (ICT5)	46.9%	49%	4.1%	0%	0%
The panelist should use recorders to capture comments during student presentation (ICT6)	0%	0%	16.3%	53.1%	30.6%
ICT encompasses wide variety of devices and applications that serve to ease and enhance efficiency during the panelist session. (ICT7)	0%	2%	2%	51%	44.9%
ICT encompasses wide variety of devices and applications that serve to ease and enhance effectiveness during the panelist session. (ICT8)	0%	0%	4.1%	44.9%	51%
It is important to use videos and recorders during student presentation. (ICT9)	0%	0%	0%	40.8%	59.2%
ICT usage enables, capturing, gathering, processing, storing, access and communication of information in different forms among the panelist and other stakeholders. (ICT10)	0%	0%	0%	55.1%	44.9%
ICT usage builds trust and fairness during presentations. (ICT 11)	0%	0%	6.1%	46.9%	46.9%

Source: Field data (2019) .

Table 3 indicates that majority of the respondents agreed that they will complete Ph.D. studies in time if the panelists use ICTs; lack of video cameras and ICT recorder in presentations affects Ph.D. progress and the quality of Ph.D. work; Presence of videos and ICT recorders in the presentation room eases the work of secretary in recording comments from panelists and improves student time management; and Presence and usage of ICTs reduces Ph.D. student financial costs. These results suggest that most of the respondents agreed that the presence of videos and ICT recorders can ease and improve both the quality of Ph.D. work and students time management. These results are not in line with Nkoyo and Nsata (2016) because this study reveals results which focused on ICT usage during panelist sessions as opposed to general usage of electronic resources by postgraduates.

Table 3. Success in Completion of Ph.D. Studies

Statements	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
I will complete my Ph.D. in time if the panelists use ICTs. (CPS 12)	0%	2%	16.3%	53.1%	28.6%
Lack of video cameras in presentations affects my Ph.D. progress. (CPS 13)	0%	2%	10.2%	46.9%	40.8%
Not using ICT recorder in presentations affects the quality of my Ph.D. work. (CPS 14)	0%	0%	2%	51%	46.9%

Presence of videos and ICT recorders in the presentation room eases the work of secretary in recording comments from panelists. (CPS 15)	0%	0%	0%	44.9%	55.1%
Presence of videos in the presentation room improves on student time management. (CPS 16)	0%	2%	2%	42.9%	53.1%
Presence and usage of ICTs reduces Ph.D. student financial costs. (CPS 17)	0%	0%	4.1%	46.9%	49%

Source: Field data (2019)

Before bootstrapping, other items were dropped due to low loadings. Collinearity values (ICT7, VIF=1.367; ICT8, VIF=1.116; ICT11, VIF=1.356, CPS13, VIF=1.049; CPS16, VIF=1.049) for the retained items indicated Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) < 4 or VIF < 5 and this is acceptable according to Hair *et al.* (2010) and Ringle *et al.* (2015) respectively.

Table 4 shows the PLS-SEM analysis using bootstrapping in predicting the relationship between ICT usage in panelist sessions and success in completion of Ph.D. studies. Table 4 indicates that T-value as 8.01. The T-value (8.01) is above 1.96 and, therefore, ICT usage in panelist sessions is a significant indicator as a predictor of success in completion of Ph.D. studies. Table 4 shows the relationship between ICT usage in panelist sessions and success in completion of Ph.D. studies is significant ($p=0.000$). This suggests that ICT7, ICT8 and ICT11 are the indicators in ICT usage in panelist sessions that predict success in completion of Ph.D. studies in terms of CPS 13 and CPS16.

The significant results of ICT usage in panelist sessions on success in completion of Ph.D. studies support the UTAUT theory. Therefore, the hypothesis is accepted and that in the context of the selected public university, ICT usage in panelist sessions predicts success in completion of Ph.D. studies. These results are contrary from Thomas and Olegajo (2017) in that the sampled respondents had low opinions on ICT whereas this study reveals that the respondents' view on ICT usage in panelist sessions had high percentages and there is a significant relationship between ICT usage in panelist sessions and success in completion of Ph.D. studies.

Table 4. T-value and P-value- ICT usage in panelist sessions and success in Completion of Ph.D. Studies (CPS)

Independent Variable	T-Value	P- Value
ICT usage in Panelist Sessions	8.01	0.000

5. CONCLUSION

This paper aimed to examine panelist sessions and Ph.D. studies. The results from the analysis of the specific objective, which aimed to analyze the relationship between ICT usage in panelist sessions and success in completions of Ph.D. studies, indicated a significant outcome. The predictors of ICT usage in panelist sessions that influence success in completion of Ph.D. studies are ICT encompasses wide variety of devices and applications that serve to ease and enhance efficiency during the panelist session; ICT encompasses wide variety of devices and applications that serve to ease and enhance effectiveness during the panelist session; and ICT usage builds trust and fairness during presentations in relation to lack of video cameras in presentations affects Ph.D. progress and presence of videos in the presentation room improves on student time management.

The theoretical implications of the findings are that ICT usage in panelist sessions and success in completion of Ph.D. studies is found to be significant in the context of the selected public

university thus supporting the UTAUT theory. The outcome of this study can assist policy makers to incorporate these predictors of ICT usage in panelist sessions for purposes of improving success in completion of Ph.D. studies. Future research can explore a similar study in other universities using qualitative methods.

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